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Research data management across borders and cultures

Working globally to find local solutions

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Abstract

As a global organisation with over 15,000 members across 150+ countries, the Research Data Alliance's (RDA)¹ strength lies in its ability to connect researchers, policymakers, and infrastructure providers to address research data management and open science challenges in an open and community driven way.

For over 10 years, the global RDA community has been developing and producing recommendations for research data management in disciplinary and organizational contexts. During this time, we have seen major shifts in technology, such as the explosion of AI, and growth in international connectivity and collaboration.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has rapidly transformed various sectors, further driven by mainstream adoption of generative AI technologies like ChatGPT. This swift progress has sparked both high expectations and uncertainties about AI's impact. AI relies on data, software, and computational resources to generate outputs like predictions and decisions. Significant investments are being made globally, both by public and private entities.

The RDA has identified AI as a strategic topic of global importance for the community. Challenges like data quality, legal issues, and the digital divide must be addressed to harness AI responsibly. Global collaboration to address these challenges is essential. It is critical that we develop standards and practices on an international scale and have the frameworks to implement them at a local and / or disciplinary level.

Since 2019, a global cohort has been working on different elements of so called "Open Science Commons" or "Data commons providing a shared virtual space or platform that offers a marketplace for data and services. Examples include the European Open Science Cloud², the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC)³, open government portals and initiatives outside traditional research contexts. Each of these initiatives provides the local research infrastructure to address the challenges presented by AI's data-intensive nature and far-reaching impact across research disciplines. Coordinating across these initiatives to

¹ Research Data Alliance (RDA – <https://www.rd-alliance.org/> (11 April 2025)

² European Open Science Cloud - EU Node <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/> (11 April 2025)

³ Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) <https://ardc.edu.au/> (11 April 2025)

enable a network of interoperable data commons is the goal of the RDA Global Open Research Commons work under the umbrella of the RDA⁴.

This session will outline the huge progress of the activity, the model developed and examples of implementation of the model in new commons, existing networks, and interoperability analysis. A new activity demonstrates how the model will be instrumental in supporting FAIR research within the health data spaces and data commons⁵.

Keywords: International collaboration, global data standards, responsible data sharing, artificial intelligence, global open research commons, cross-disciplinary and multidisciplinary research data management.

Resources

The material and resources (e.g. data, model, codes, documentation, videos) which underly, support or are closely related to your contribution deposited on a repository, please include a title, the respective DOI(s) and brief description. E.g.

- My Software. <https://doi.org/.....> "Software that enables."

Author contributions

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

Not applicable

Acknowledgement

We would like to acknowledge the activities executed by the volunteer global Research Data Alliance community through the Working and Interest groups and Communities of Practice.

References

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- ⁴ RDA GORC International Implementations Working Group
<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/gorc-international-implementations-working-group-gorc-ii-wg/activity/> (11 April 2025)
- ⁵ RDA Health Data Commons GORC Profile WG
<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/health-data-commons-gorc-profile-wg/activity/> (11 April 2025)